

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No6(5)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 344 sahifa,
16-iyun, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – “Yangi O'zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: “Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon” MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Tinglovchilarga axloqiy-estetik tarbiya berishda notiqlik madaniyatini shakllantirishning samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlari	10
<i>Fazliddin Abdunabiyevich Abdurazaqov</i>	
Professor-o'qituvchilarning ilmiy-pedagogik salohiyatini xalqaro mezonlar asosida rivojlantirish yo'llari	15
<i>Maxmudov Qudratbek Shavkat o'g'li</i>	
Orfografik kompetensiyaning mohiyati va boshlang'ich sinflarda shakllanish bosqichlari	21
<i>Abduvaliyeva Nodira Alisherovna, Mo'minjonova Gulnoraxon Abdupatto qizi</i>	
Tabiiy fanlarni o'qitishda uch o'lchamli vizualizatsiyalarning boshlang'ich ta'limdagi ahamiyati	25
<i>Nabijonova Feruza Valijon qizi</i>	
Loyiha texnologiyasi asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda ijtimoiy tashabbuskorlikni rivojlantirish mazmuni	28
<i>O'rinova Nilufar Muxammadovna</i>	
Sinfdan tashqari o'qish darslarida badiiy asar bilan ishlashning kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosidagi metodikasi	32
<i>Qilichova Billura Yorqinxuja qizi, Homidov H. K.</i>	
Kasbiy-kommunikativ madaniyat fenomenining pedagogik talqini va rivojlanish tendensiyalari	37
<i>Tashpulatova Nodira Olimjon qizi</i>	
Tabiiy fanlarni o'qitishda kompetensiyaviy yondashuv	41
<i>Umbarova Nasiba Xolboy qizi</i>	
Xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda shaxs nutqining shakllanishida psixolingvistikaning ahamiyati	44
<i>Ahmedov Shavkat Asadilloevich, Ataboev Navruz Ihombek o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida matnni tushunish va tahlil qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi (PIRLS dasturi misolida)	47
<i>Abduraxmanova Charos Burxanovna</i>	
Lesson Planning in English Language Teaching at Technical Universities	51
<i>Aitbaeva Nursuliu Tairbekovna</i>	
Lingvistik intellekt asosida individual o'qitish yondashuvining samaradorligi	55
<i>Allanazarova Sadoqat Azimovna</i>	
Xorij tadqiqotlarida zamonaviy oila transformatsiyasida farzandlar taraqqiyotining ijtimoiy-psixologik asoslari	59
<i>Bo'riyeva Mahbuba Shavkatovna</i>	
Теоретико-методологические подходы к изучению эмоциональных концептов в литературе: (на материале английских и немецких фразеологизмов)	63
<i>Сайёра Улашевна Тагаева, Азиза Анкаевна Уразкулова</i>	
The Importance of Forming a Schedule for High School Students	67
<i>D. T. Atabayeva, X. I. Abduraymova</i>	
Milliy cholg'u ansambllari orqali o'quvchilar musiqiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirish	70
<i>Dadamirzayeva Gulshanoy To'lanjon qizi</i>	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyaga yondashuvning texnologik xususiyatlari ...	75
<i>Jumanov Sherzod Saloyevich</i>	
Adabiyot darsliklari uchun yangi o'zbek adabiyoti namunalarini saralashning ilmiy-metodik asoslari	78
<i>Musaboyeva Zulfira Iqboljon qizi</i>	
Maktab geometriyasida ko'pyoqlilar mavzusini o'rganishning innovatsion usullari	83
<i>Pirlepesov Umrbek Baxtiyor o'g'li</i>	
Generativ AI vositalarining mustaqil ta'lim jarayonidagi didaktik funksiyalari	86
<i>Qahramonova Xumora Qahramonovna</i>	
O'quvchi-sportchilar uchun individual mashg'ulot yuklamalarini avtomatik rejalashtirish va optimallashtirish imkoniyatini yaratish ahamiyati	91
<i>Qosimov Faxriddin Jo'raqulovich</i>	

Когнитивный диссонанс как социально-психологический феномен в контексте высшего образования: теоретический анализ	95
Мансурова Гульмира Рафазловна	
Регуляторный произвол или необходимый порядок? Влияние новых регуляторных механизмов на свободу расследовательской журналистики	101
Рауфова Озода	
Qizlar tarbiyasida mahalla–oila–maktab hamkorligi mexanizmlari	105
Choriyeva Dildora Ismat qizi	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarini individuallashtirishning samaradorligi: kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida	109
Tangriyev Abdulkarim Tovashevich	
O'qish savodxonligi darslarida matn bilan ishlash orqali o'quvchilarda muammoli vaziyatlarni hal etish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi.....	114
Boymurodova Nodirabegim Bahodir qizi	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida STEAM ta'limi orqali talabalarda tanqidiy fikrlash kompetensiyasini shakllantirish	120
Kozimova Mehriniso Akbarali qizi	
Oliy ta'limda kvest texnologiyasi yordamida fizika fanining murakkab tushunchalarini o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish metodikasi.....	125
O'rinboyeva Kumushoy Sultonbek qizi	
Tasvirlarga raqamli ishlov berish texnologiyalari va ularning amaliy qo'llanilishi	129
Sharipov Nodir Botir o'g'li	
Management of Medical Emergencies in Outpatient Dental Clinics.....	133
Adurazzoqov Kamoliddin, Umarov Maruf, Buzrukhoda Javohir	
Psixologik farovonlikning asosiy komponentlari, ta'sir qiluvchi omillar va zamonaviy baholash usullari	138
Aliyev Samariddin Murotali o'g'li	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	142
Boymurodova Sadoqat Istam qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi ta'lim tizimi.....	146
Gadoymurodova Kamola Sunnatulloevna	
Oilada bola tarbiyasining ahamiyati va uning shaxs kamolotiga ta'siri	151
Galdiyeva Mehribon Durdiyevna, Oilimova Mushtariy Xaydarali qizi	
Art-pedagogika vositasida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida estetik dunyoqarashni shakllantirishning pedagogik ahamiyati	154
Gulboyev Akbar Tuxtyayevich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ma'naviy tadbirlar orqali vatanparvarlik tuyg'usini shakllantirish	158
Homidov Husniddin Kupaysinovich, Yusupova Gulzor Yunusjon qizi, Norbekova Sevinch Musurmon qizi	
Bone-Grafting Materials in Oral Surgery: Classification, Biological Properties, and Clinical Application	161
Jumaqulova Mashhura Alishevovna, Buzrukhoda Javohir Davronovich	
Mediatsiya va o'qib tushunish kompetensiyasi o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqadorlik	166
Karimova Dilyoraxon Raximjon qizi	
Using STEM Technologies to Foster Rational Thinking in the Dentistry	169
Khonimqulov Javlon, Burkhonova Zarafuz	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini montessori metodikasi vositasida til o'rganish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish usullari modeli.....	173
Mahbuba Yusupova Rustam qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda tayanch kompetensiyalarni integrativ yondashuv asosida shakllantirish metodikasining samaradorligi.....	177
Nasimova N. Q.	
Analysis of Scanning Techniques Used in Orthodontic Dentistry	182
Nasrullayev Javlonbek Ta'atonovich, Rahimberdiyev Rustam Abdunosirovich	
Zamonaviylik - ta'lim konsepsiyasida asosiy mezon sifatida	187
Ochilova Gulnoza Odilovna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	O'qish savodxonligi darslarida xalq og'zaki ijodidan foydalanish metodikasi 191 Qahhorova Sojida Bahodir qizi, Zokirov Javoxir G'aybullo o'g'li	191
	Diqqat va xotira jarayonlarida raqamli texnologiyalarning roli 196 Salomova Nargiza Sattorovna	196
	Talabalarda kasbiy refleksiya rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi psixologik omillarning empirik tahlili..... 200 Shukurova Nargiza Ikramovna	200
	Gimnastikachi qizlarda egiluvchanlik jismoniy sifatini rivojlantirish jarayonida shikastlanishlarning oldini olish 205 Sultanova Musharafxon Xudoyqul qizi	205
	Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda ekologik bilimlarni raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida rivojlantirish... 210 Sayfetdinova Dildora Ikramitdinovna	210
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning rivojlanishida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan texnologiyalardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, imkoniyatlari va yo'nalishlari 216 Uralova Nurxon Maxadovna	216
	Naqshbandiya qadriyatlarini bo'lg'usi o'qituvchi shaxsini shakllantirishdagi o'rni..... 220 Xalmuxamedova Maxbuba Aslanovna	220
	Boshlang'ich ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari 223 Xo'jamberdiyeva Maftuna Norqobilovna, Sanaqulova Sevinch Baxtiyor qizi	223
	Developing Logical Thinking via the Use of STEM Technology 226 Yarmuhammedov Nabijon Navruzovich, Burkhonova Zarafuz	226
	Jismoniy tarbiya darslarida innovatsion metodlardan foydalanishning ahamiyati 229 Yo'ldoshboyeva Zulfiya Ravshan qizi, Jumayev Abdilxakim Turdiyevich	229
	Значение предмета физического воспитания и спортивной метрологии в физическом воспитании молодежи 233 Маматкулов Равшанжон Солижонович	233
	Аксиологические аспекты диалога культур в романе Сухбата Афлатуни "Рай Земной" 237 Чернова Татьяна Алексеевна, Худойназаров Сардорбек	237
	Maktab boshqaruvida ilmiy asoslangan yondashuvlarni joriy etishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari..... 240 Akbutayeva Gulasal Uzoq qizi	240
	Features of Verbal and Non-Verbal Communication in Teaching Foreign Languages in Higher Education Institutions 248 Gulnoza Aslamovna Azimkulova	248
	Chaenomeles Japonica (Thunb.) Lindl. Ex Spach mevalaridan ajratib olingan polifenol va pektin komplekslarining ichak mikrobiotasi, oksidlovchi stress va immun javobga ta'sirini molekulyar-biologik usullar asosida tadqiq etish 251 Ergasheva Nigora G'ayratovna	251
	Contemporary Linguodidactic Trends in Teaching English in Higher Education 259 Khudoyarova Ziyoda Maratovna	259
	Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning muammo va imkoniyatlari..... 264 Layloxon Xabibullayeva Tursunali qizi	264
	Raqamli sport pedagogikasi va bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish omillari..... 269 Matvapayev Azizbek Gaibnazar o'g'li	269
	Sun'iy intellektga qaramlik: raqamli addiksiya evolyutsiyasining yangi bosqichi 273 Mo'minxo'jayeva Zuhra Alimjon qizi	273
	Linguo-Cognitive Modeling of The Relationship Between Life and Death In Literary Texts: a Comparative Analysis (Based on 20 th -Century English and Karakalpak Works)..... 279 Najimova Perizad Arslanbay qizi	279
	Talabalar intellektual qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning didaktik imkoniyatlari 283 Shodiyeva Charos Ravshan qizi	283
	Ta'limiy o'yinlar vositasida ko'zi ojiz bolalar nutqidagi kamchiliklarni korreksiyalashga qaratilgan mashg'ulotlarining asosiy bosqichlari 286 Xaytova Farida Kuchkarovna	286

Raqamli va an'anaviy o'qish: qiyosiy tahlil.....	292
<i>Mashrapova Sevara Xabibovna</i>	
Mustahkam oila qadriyatlari va ularning zamonaviy jamiyat rivojiga ta'siri.....	296
<i>Soyibova Bonu O'tkir qizi</i>	
Sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirishning pedagogik mohiyati	301
<i>Xoliqov Farxod Karomatillo o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalar: sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan oqilona foydalanish metodikasi...	305
<i>Aminov Shavkatjon Sobir o'g'li, Abdusattarova Muhlisaxon Foziljon qizi, Berdiyaroova Jasmena Sherzodjon qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik bosqichidagi dzyudochilarda koordinatsion qobiliyatlarni shakllantirishning samarali vositalari	311
<i>Jumanova Iroda Shokirjon qizi</i>	
Mediatsiya va o'qib tushunish kompEtensiyasi o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqadorlik.....	315
<i>Karimova Dilyoraxon Raximjon qizi</i>	
Xorijiy tillarda yozma ish turlarini o'rganishning o'ziga xos jihatlari	319
<i>Omonova Sarvinoz</i>	
Can Duolingo Reduce Speaking Anxiety: A Literature-Based Analysis	322
<i>Qodirqulova Ra'no</i>	
Kommunikativ yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarning chet tilida muloqot qilish ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirish	326
<i>Sa'dullayeva Shahzoda Nuriddin qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy psixologning kasbiy kompetensiyasi: krizisli vaziyatlarda ishlash texnologiyalari.....	330
<i>Shirinov Otabek Tuvalovich</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning rivojlanishida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan texnologiyalardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, imkoniyatlari va yo'nalishlari	333
<i>Uralova Nurxon Maxadovna</i>	
Иммерсивные технологии в обучении русскому языку как иностранному: современные подходы и перспективы	337
<i>Абдусаламова Адига Каримджановна</i>	
Инновационная методика интенсивного обучения студентов филологического направления русскому языку в сопоставлении с узбекским языком	340
<i>Касимов А. Б.</i>	

CONTEMPORARY LINGUODIDACTIC TRENDS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Khudoyarova Ziyoda Maratovna

Tashkent State University of Economics,
 Associate Professor at the Department of Foreign Language Education,
 (PhD) Doctor of Philosophy in Psychology

Abstract: This article examines the modern linguodidactic trends in teaching English in higher education institutions based on a scientific, theoretical, and comparative analysis. The study focuses on the impact of communicative language teaching, task-based language teaching (TBLT), Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), and digital learning technologies on the effectiveness of English language instruction. Based on the analysis of scientific literature and meta-analytical findings, the role of these approaches in developing students' linguistic, communicative, and academic competencies is investigated. The study also identifies the ongoing modernization of English language teaching in higher education and the shift toward a competency-based approach, substantiating its practical significance. The results demonstrate that the systematic implementation of modern linguodidactic approaches is a crucial factor in enhancing educational quality and preparing specialists in accordance with international standards.

Key words: linguodidactics, higher education, English language teaching, communicative approach, TBLT, CLIL, digital education, competency-based approach.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada oliy ta'lim tizimida ingliz tilini o'qitishning zamonaviy lingvodidaktik tendensiyalari ilmiy-nazariy va qiyosiy tahlil asosida o'rganildi. Tadqiqotda kommunikativ yondashuv, vazifaga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim (TBLT), fan va til integratsiyasiga asoslangan CLIL modeli hamda raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalarining ingliz tili o'qitish samaradorligiga ta'siri yoritildi. Ilmiy adabiyotlar va meta-tahlil natijalari asosida ushbu yondashuvlarning talabalarning lingvistik, kommunikativ va akademik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilindi. Shuningdek, oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonining modernizatsiyasi va kompetensiyaviy yondashuvga o'tish tendensiyalari aniqlanib, ularning amaliy ahamiyati asoslab berildi. Tadqiqot natijalari zamonaviy lingvodidaktik yondashuvlarni tizimli joriy etish ta'lim sifatini oshirish va xalqaro standartlarga mos mutaxassislar tayyorlashda muhim omil ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvodidaktika, oliy ta'lim, ingliz tilini o'qitish, kommunikativ yondashuv, TBLT, CLIL, raqamli ta'lim, kompetensiyaviy yondashuv.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются современные лингводидактические тенденции преподавания английского языка в системе высшего образования на основе научно-теоретического и сравнительного анализа. Исследование направлено на изучение влияния коммуникативного подхода, обучения на основе задач (TBLT), интегрированного обучения предмету и языку (CLIL), а также цифровых образовательных технологий на эффективность преподавания английского языка. На основе анализа научной литературы и результатов мета-аналитических исследований рассматривается роль данных подходов в развитии лингвистической, коммуникативной и академической компетенций студентов. Также выявлены процессы модернизации преподавания английского языка в высшей школе и переход к компетентностному подходу, что подтверждает их практическую значимость. Результаты исследования показывают, что системное внедрение современных лингводидактических подходов является важным фактором повышения качества образования и подготовки специалистов в соответствии с международными стандартами.

Ключевые слова: лингводидактика, высшее образование, преподавание английского языка, коммуникативный подход, TBLT, CLIL, цифровое образование, компетентностный подход.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of contemporary globalization processes, teaching English in higher education institutions is regarded not only as a means of developing communicative competence but also as a key strategic factor in enhancing students' academic, professional, and scientific potential at an international level. In particular, ongoing transformations in modern linguodidactics necessitate a fundamental renewal of English language teaching methodologies, shifting from traditional approaches toward models based on communicative, competency-based, and digital learning technologies.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, systematic reforms are being implemented to modernize the education system, improve the quality of foreign language instruction, and align it with international standards. In this regard, the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 6, 2022, No. PF-165¹, "On Measures for the Implementation of the Innovation Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," adopted with the aim of advancing innovative development of the education system, widely introducing digital technologies, and strengthening integration into the global educational space, serves as one of the key legal foundations for modernizing foreign language teaching methodology in higher education institutions. These initiatives are significantly contributing to the qualitative advancement of English language education in universities ^[1].

From this perspective, it is of particular importance to conduct a scientific analysis of the evolution of linguo-didactic approaches in English language teaching, as well as the impact of modern methodologies such as CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), blended learning, task-based learning, and digital learning environments. These trends not only enhance the effectiveness of language acquisition but also expand opportunities for students' integration into global academic and professional environments.

This article provides a theoretical and scientific analysis of contemporary linguodidactic trends in teaching English in higher education and substantiates their effectiveness in practical educational settings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent scientific studies on contemporary linguodidactic trends in teaching English in higher education indicate a shift from communicative approaches toward competency-based and digitally integrated learning models. In this regard, both international and local scholars have developed significant theoretical frameworks and pedagogical concepts.

Among foreign literature, Douglas H. Brown's "Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy" (2007) provides a systematic overview of communicative foundations in language teaching. The author emphasizes the importance of interactivity, learner-centered instruction, and the use of authentic materials in language education. This conceptual framework contributes to enhancing the effectiveness of English language teaching in modern higher education environments ^[2].

Similarly, David Nunan's "Task-Based Language Teaching" (2004) establishes a theoretical foundation for task-based language teaching (TBLT). According to Nunan, language acquisition is most effective when it occurs through the completion of real communicative tasks. This approach serves as an important methodological basis for preparing students for academic and professional discourse in higher education settings ^[3].

In "Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching" (2014), Jack C. Richards and Theodore S. Rodgers analyze the evolution of language teaching methodologies, highlighting the development of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), audio-lingual, and eclectic approaches. The authors emphasize that modern linguo-didactics is characterized not by rigid methodological boundaries but by the integration of diverse approaches ^[4].

In the European educational context, the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) model developed by Do Coyle ("CLIL - Content and Language Integrated Learning", 2010) is of particular significance. This approach involves teaching English not as an isolated subject but in integration with other academic disciplines. Consequently, it expands opportunities for learning the language in functional and academic contexts within higher education ^[5].

Within local academic literature, important studies have also been conducted on English language teaching methodology. In particular, J. Jalolov's "Chet til o'qitish metodikasi" (Methodology of Foreign Language Teaching) (2012) scientifically substantiates the didactic principles of foreign language teaching, lesson organization methods, and the foundations of communicative approaches. The author emphasizes the necessity of adapting methodological approaches to the context of the Uzbek education system ^[6].

Furthermore, research conducted by M. Mahkamova (2022) analyzes the use of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching English in higher education, particularly the effectiveness of interactive methods and multimedia tools. These studies empirically demonstrate the positive impact of digital learning environments on language acquisition efficiency ^[7].

In addition, state policy aimed at modernizing the foreign language education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan serves as an important foundation for scientific research. In particular, reforms initiated under the leadership of Shavkat Mirziyoyev, including the implementation of competency-based education and the widespread adoption of digital technologies, have directly contributed to the development of contemporary linguodidactic trends.

¹ <https://lex.uz/docs/-6102462>

Overall, the analyzed foreign and local literature indicates that English language teaching methodology is transitioning from traditional grammar-based instruction toward communicative, competency-based, and digitally integrated models. At the same time, approaches such as CLT, TBLT, and CLIL are emerging as key methodological directions in enhancing the effectiveness of linguodidactic processes in higher education institutions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is aimed at providing a scientific examination of contemporary linguodidactic trends in teaching English in higher education institutions, and it is based on a comprehensive methodological approach. The theoretical framework of the research is grounded in scholarly perspectives in the fields of foreign language education, communicative methodology, competency-based instruction, and digital pedagogy.

During the research process, the method of systematic literature review was employed to examine modern concepts of English language teaching, including Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), and blended learning approaches. Through comparative analysis, the methodological potential of these approaches and their impact on instructional effectiveness were identified.

In addition, methods of analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, classification, and scientific generalization were applied. These methods enabled the systematization of the main trends in linguodidactic development and the evaluation of their significance in higher education practice.

The reliability of the research findings was ensured through the comparative analysis of local and international academic sources, the conceptual synthesis of existing theoretical perspectives, and the integration of scientific conclusions related to contemporary educational practice. This methodological approach made it possible to interpret current trends in English language education as an integrated scientific system.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The conducted analysis confirms that contemporary linguodidactic approaches have a significant impact on the effectiveness of English language education. In particular, a meta-analysis conducted by Lara Bryfonski and Todd McKay, based on 52 empirical studies, revealed that the overall effect size of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) was $d = 0.93$. This indicates a strong positive effect on language learning outcomes. The researchers report that in TBLT-based instruction, students demonstrate higher levels of communicative engagement, fluency, and practical language competence compared to traditional teaching methods^[8].

These findings suggest that, in modern higher education contexts, language acquisition is more effective when students learn through the completion of real communicative tasks rather than through the study of theoretical rules alone. In particular, for students preparing for professional careers, task-based instruction plays a crucial role in developing practical communicative competencies.

In recent years, the effectiveness of task repetition has also been empirically validated. According to a 2025 meta-analysis published in the journal *System*, task repetition significantly improves learners' syntactic complexity and grammatical accuracy. In particular, a reduction in spoken errors and an increased use of complex sentence structures were observed^[9].

These results demonstrate that repetition in language learning is not merely a memorization strategy but also an important mechanism for the automatization of linguistic units. Accordingly, the repeated performance of the same communicative tasks in different contexts contributes to the stable development of learners' language skills.

The analysis also revealed the high effectiveness of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) and English Medium Instruction (EMI) models. A meta-analysis conducted by Jang Ho Lee, Hansol Lee, and Yuen Yi Lo, encompassing 44 studies and 7,434 learners, found that EMI-CLIL programs had a positive effect on English language competence, with effect sizes ranging from $d = 0.73$ to $d = 1.01$ ^[10].

These findings confirm the necessity of teaching English not as an isolated subject but as a medium for acquiring disciplinary and academic knowledge. In particular, the use of CLIL and EMI approaches in fields such as economics, tourism, information technology, and international relations enables the simultaneous development of both language proficiency and subject-specific competencies.

The digital transformation of English language teaching in higher education has also emerged as a significant factor. A meta-analysis conducted by Hamad H. Alsowat, covering 3,496 studies, found that technology-based language teaching methods yielded an effect size of $d = 0.98$ for vocabulary development and $d = 1.26$ for grammatical competence^[11].

These findings confirm the importance of digital technologies in enhancing educational effectiveness. However, technology alone does not guarantee learning outcomes; its effectiveness depends on pedagogically

appropriate application, integration with interactive methods, and support for students' independent learning activities.

OECD reports also emphasize that digital learning environments, artificial intelligence tools, and adaptive learning platforms contribute to the individualization of the educational process, allowing instruction to be tailored to learners' pace and needs (Table 1).

Table 1: Comparative Analytical Framework of Modern Linguodidactic Approaches

Approach	Core Idea	Advantages	Impact on Higher Education
CLT (Communicative Language Teaching)	Teaching language as a means of communication	Develops real communicative competence	Enhances students' spoken fluency and classroom interaction
TBLT (Task-Based Language Teaching)	Learning through completion of meaningful tasks	Strengthens practical language skills	Improves ability to use language in problem-solving situations
CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning)	Integration of subject content and language learning	Simultaneous development of academic and language skills	Promotes formation of professional English competence
Digital Learning / AI-based Learning	Technology-enhanced language instruction	Personalized learning and immediate feedback	Enhances learner autonomy and flexible learning environment

Overall, the analysis demonstrates that the main developmental directions of modern linguodidactics are closely associated with communicativeness, task orientation, content-language integration, and digitalization. These trends not only enhance English language competence but also contribute to the development of critical thinking, independent learning skills, and professional communication abilities. Therefore, the integrated application of these approaches is considered essential in organizing English language instruction in higher education institutions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study indicate that the process of teaching English in higher education institutions is undergoing a qualitative transition to a new stage under the influence of contemporary linguodidactic approaches. The analysis confirms that communicative language teaching, Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), and digitally enhanced learning environments significantly contribute to the development of students' linguistic, communicative, and academic competencies.

It has been established that the dominant direction of modern linguodidactics is the teaching of English not as an isolated academic subject, but as a medium for professional and academic activity. This trend contributes not only to the development of students' language proficiency but also to their ability to function in the international information space, think critically, engage in academic communication, and develop autonomous learning skills.

The reviewed scholarly sources and meta-analytical findings demonstrate that the effectiveness of modern linguodidactic technologies is well supported by empirical evidence. Therefore, the systematic integration of innovative methods into educational practice is of crucial importance for the renewal of English language teaching content.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- to improve English language curricula on the basis of communicative and competency-based approaches;
- to more widely implement CLIL and EMI elements based on the integration of subject-specific content and English language learning;
- to expand the use of artificial intelligence technologies, adaptive learning platforms, and digital educational resources;
- to enhance continuous professional development programs aimed at improving teachers' modern linguodidactic and digital competencies;
- to extend empirical research focused on evaluating the effectiveness of contemporary linguodidactic approaches in higher education institutions of Uzbekistan.

In conclusion, the consistent implementation of modern linguodidactic trends in higher education practice is one of the key factors in improving the quality of English language education, preparing specialists with competencies aligned with international standards, and strengthening the country's competitiveness in the global academic and professional arena.

References:

1. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2022, July 6). Decree No. PF–165 “On measures to implement the Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022–2026”. Tashkent. <https://lex.uz/docs/-6102462>
2. D.H.Douglas Brown (2007) “Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy”, Pearson ESL. 569 p. https://openlibrary.org/books/OL9654428M/Teaching_by_Principles
3. David Nunan (2004) “Task-Based Language Teaching”, Cambridge University Press. 222 p.
4. https://books.google.co.uz/books?id=wBKoWKodDk0C&redir_esc=y
5. Jack C. Richards, Theodore S. Rodgers (2022) “Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching” Cambridge University Press <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009024532>
6. Do Coyle (2010) “CLIL: Content and Language Integrated Learning”, Cambridge University Press https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262450443_CLIL_Content_and_Language_Integrated_Learning
7. J. Jalolov (2012) “Chet til o‘qitish metodikasi” (Methodology of Foreign Language Teaching), O‘qituvchi. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?q=Jalolov+Chet+til+o%27qitish+metodikasi>
8. Mahkamova. M. (2022) “Interactive teaching methods in English language lessons”, American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 11, 309-314. <https://ajird.journalspark.org/index.php/ajird/article/view/439>
9. L. Bryfonski (2017) “TBLT implementation and evaluation: A meta-analysis”, Sage Journals, 23(5). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168817744389>
10. Abdi Tabari et al. (2025). “Task repetition and L2 oral performance: A meta-analysis. System”, System, 135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2025.103868>
11. Jang Ho Lee et al. (2023). “Effects of EMI-CLIL on secondary-level students’ English learning: A multilevel meta-analysis”, Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching, 13(2), 317–345. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssl.38277>
12. Hamad H. Alsowat (2020). “Evidence-Based Practices of English Language Teaching: A Meta-Analysis of Meta-Analyses”, English Language Teaching, 13(11). <https://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/elt/article/view/0/44029>

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №6(5)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.